

The further away the better? Factors influencing the public's location preferences for mobile phone base stations. A 10-country study

Sarah C. Link^{a,*}, Leanne Martin^b, James Grellier^b, Marie Eggeling-Böcker^a, Ferdinand Abacioglu^a, Carolin Schulz^a, Nina Vaupotič^c, Mathew P. White^d, Christoph Boehmert^{a,e}

^a Department for Social Sciences, IU International University of Applied Sciences, Juri-Gagarin Ring 152, 99084, Erfurt, Germany

^b Public Health and Sport Sciences, University of Exeter Medical School, University of Exeter, Peter Lanyon Building 12, Penryn, Cornwall, TR10 8RD, UK

^c Department of Cognition, Emotion, and Methods in Psychology, University of Vienna, Wächtergasse 1, 1010, Vienna, Austria

^d Department of Clinical and Health Psychology, University of Vienna, Wächtergasse 1, 1010, Vienna, Austria

^e Aalen University of Applied Sciences, Beethovenstraße 1, 73430, Aalen, Germany

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Mobile communication
5G
Location preferences
Visual amenity
Distance-decay
Non-ionizing radiation
Exposure

ABSTRACT

New mobile phone base stations are frequently opposed by the public, even though mobile phones are used by most of the population. While such reaction has often been described as NIMBYism ('not in my back yard'), this label offers little insight into the psychological mechanisms underlying such opposition. The present mixed-methods research moves beyond a simple NIMBY interpretation through an in-depth investigation of public location preferences for 4G-plus 5G-capable base stations. Study 1 included six focus groups conducted in December 2022, and Study 2 was a ten-country survey ($n = 10,358$) conducted between September–December 2023. In both studies, participants were asked to select their preferred base station site from six hypothetical locations and indicate the reasons underlying their choice. Overall, many participants followed one of two siting approaches: approach A preferring locations 'as far away as possible', and approach B preferring the 'least visually appealing' location. While in Study 1 participants tended to follow approach B (16 out of 35), in Study 2 approach A was followed most frequently (53.6%). Among the reasons surveyed, distance had the greatest influence on location preferences, followed by reception, exposure to EMFs, and visual appearance. Distance and EMF were strongly correlated ($r = .531$), which is why we assume that distance was a proxy for reduced exposure. However, greater distance can in fact increase overall exposure due to the increased power required for higher handset transmission. Age, gender, risk perception, exposure perception, use of 5G, acceptance and the expected impact of 5G were also associated with the choice of location. We found that widespread public communication efforts are needed to explain how 5G technology works, and that other issues such as visual amenity also need to be sensitively managed. Our results inform the broader discourse on base station siting: communication between stakeholders needs to be improved, fostering mutual understanding of preferences, and guiding decision-making for both telecommunication companies and the public.

1. Introduction

Infrastructure projects are frequently rejected by the general public for a multitude of reasons. Such rejection has affected the viability of renewable energies such as wind power (e.g., van der Horst, 2007a), tidal power (e.g., Devine-Wright, 2011) and solar energy (e.g., Carlisle et al., 2016), as well as, for example, the expansion of power grids (e.g., Lienert et al., 2017; Wiedemann & Claus, 2013; Wiedemann et al., 2018)

and the mobile communications network (e.g., Hermans, 2015; TNS Opinion & Social, 2010). In this paper, we examine public preferences regarding the siting of mobile phone masts ('base stations').

Typically, consumer mobile communications transmit radio-frequency electromagnetic fields (RF-EMF) between a mobile phone and a base station to facilitate calls and data transmission. The underlying technologies constantly evolve to enable ever faster data transmission rates. The rollout of the latest mobile communications standard,

* Corresponding author. IU International University of Applied Sciences, Juri-Gagarin-Ring 152, D-99084, Erfurt, Germany.

E-mail address: sarah.link@tuwien.ac.at (S.C. Link).

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvp.2026.103070>

Received 13 September 2025; Received in revised form 6 May 2026; Accepted 7 May 2026

Available online 8 May 2026

0272-4944/© 2026 The Authors. Published by Elsevier Ltd. This is an open access article under the CC BY license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

5G, began in Europe in 2019, building on earlier standards (2G/GSM, 3G/UMTS, 4G/LTE). In Europe 89% of populated areas had 5G network coverage in 2023 (European Commission, 2024).

Over the past 20 years, the public has increasingly perceived the health risks related to RF-EMF used in mobile communications as low (cf. Boehmert, 2018; Goette & Ludewig, 2019, 2024). Nevertheless, the proportion of the population that believes such RF-EMF poses a risk to health differs greatly between European countries (range: 16% in Denmark, 81% in Greece; TNS Opinion & Social, 2010). At the same time, public resistance to the rapid expansion of 5G networks gained momentum during the pandemic, partly due to misinformation campaigns linking COVID-19 to 5G (Keystone-SDA, 2019). Despite various public information campaigns, opinion on 5G has remained divided (Dashtipour et al., 2021; Herrera-Contreras et al., 2020; YouGov, 2021), which stands in contrast to the very high market penetration of mobile phone use.

Potential health risks of RF-EMF emitted by mobile communications technologies have been assessed by international institutions like the International Commission on Non-Ionizing Radiation Protection (ICNIRP), the World Health Organization (WHO), and the International Agency for Research on Cancer (IARC). In 2013, IARC classified RF-EMF from mobile phones as possibly carcinogenic (IARC, 2013). According to ICNIRP and WHO, the weight of evidence indicates no adverse health effects below the existing threshold values (ICNIRP, 2009; WHO, 2020). The only clear biological effect that has been identified is that of tissue heating.

More recently, the WHO commissioned a series of ten systematic reviews based on a survey with 164 leading experts in the field of RF-EMF (Verbeek et al., 2021), focusing on six possible health outcomes. These reviews, along with a contextual summary (Verbeek et al., 2025), reported: moderate to high certainty evidence for no or only minor effects of RF-EMF on cancer (in humans), cognition, and symptoms, while there was high certainty evidence from animal studies for a significant impairment of male fertility. For other endpoints, such as oxidative stress, thyroid cancer, or fertility in humans, the evidence is currently very limited or contradictory (Verbeek et al., 2025). To date, neither ICNIRP nor IARC have updated their risk assessment based on these reviews.

1.1. Reasons for rejection of base stations in close proximity

A review of the literature on public responses to infrastructure siting, particularly base stations, identifies three recurring reasons for rejection: exposure reduction, visual amenity, and procedural justice (Betakova et al., 2015; Carlisle et al., 2016; Claassen et al., 2014; Cousin & Siegrist, 2010a; Dilkova-Gnoyke et al., 2022; Dohle et al., 2010; Hermans, 2015; Lienert et al., 2017; Link et al., 2025). Other factors may also contribute but are not the focus here.

A frequently used concept to explain local opposition to infrastructure is 'NIMBY' ('not in my backyard'). According to this view, people may generally support and use a technology, such as mobile communications, but resist related infrastructure in their immediate vicinity. While widely applied, the NIMBY concept has been criticized for its simplicity and for overemphasizing a 'selfish' element (e.g., Devine-Wright, 2009; 2011; van der Horst, 2007b). More recent research suggests that local opposition is often better understood through the lens of place attachment, which refers to the emotional and symbolic bonds people form with their home or community (Devine-Wright & Batel, 2017). Place attachment encompasses motives such as the protection and conservation of valued places and can reflect both personal and collective concerns (Perlaviciute et al., 2018, 2021). Importantly, place attachment can shape responses to infrastructure both in terms of perceived exposure, visual impacts, and procedural justice.

Exposure reduction: Given the complexity of mobile communications technology, many members of the public have only a relatively superficial understanding of how mobile communications work and may also

hold misconceptions (Cousin & Siegrist, 2010a; Vaupotić et al., 2025). These misconceptions may lead residents to oppose nearby base stations based on inaccurate assumptions about exposure to RF-EMF.

When transmitting voice or data, mobile phones interact with base stations. During this interaction, both emit RF-EMF. The strength of the RF-EMF field decreases quickly with increasing distance from the source. Since mobile phones are so much closer to their users than base stations, their relative contribution to personal exposure is usually higher than that of base stations. As a result, overall exposure is mostly higher when base stations are located further away, because mobile phones must increase emissions to reach the base station. Studies indicate that this is counterintuitive for lay persons (Claassen et al., 2014; Cousin & Siegrist, 2010a; Dilkova-Gnoyke et al., 2022). Consequently, the public often overestimates exposure from base stations and underestimates that of their own devices.

From a place attachment perspective, opposition to nearby base stations may therefore not only stem from misconceptions about exposure, but also from a desire to protect one's immediate living environment from possible risks. In this sense, resistance can reflect place-based concerns related to safety and the preservation of the home environment.

Visual amenity: Visual considerations also influence infrastructure acceptance. Betakova et al. (2015) and Carlisle et al. (2016) looked specifically into the factors influencing acceptance of new wind turbines and photovoltaic systems, respectively. Both concluded that visible infrastructure is more likely to be rejected in places that are considered visually attractive and worth protecting compared to those considered unattractive and less worthy of protection. This is consistent with Lienert et al. (2017), who investigated the influence of affect on the acceptance of high-voltage power lines depending on the type of landscape. In this context, high-voltage power lines triggered a stronger negative affect in areas with a more natural landscape than in urban areas. It is therefore likely that people tend to reject infrastructure in visually attractive and meaningful areas to protect their sense of place and identity.

Similarly, aesthetics can also have an influence on controversies about new base stations (Hermans, 2015). Dohle et al. (2010) showed that camouflaged or concealed antennas are preferred over visible ones.

These findings support the role of place attachment, as visually valued environments are more likely to be protected against perceived intrusions, reinforcing conservation-oriented motives.

Procedural justice: Beyond exposure and visual concerns, voluntariness or perceived fairness can also influence acceptance. People voluntarily expose themselves to RF-EMF emitted by their mobile phone. But when a base station is built in the neighborhood, they may believe that potential risks are imposed on them (cf. Starr, 1969). Hermans (2015) found that affected residents would like to have a say and be involved in location decisions. Moreover, people may associate more direct benefits with mobile phones than they do with base stations (Link et al., 2025). While procedural justice has been identified as an important determinant of infrastructure acceptance, particularly in participatory planning contexts, the present study focuses on cognitive and affective evaluations of siting options rather than on decision-making procedures themselves.

1.2. Location preferences

In addition to the reasons that could lead to the rejection of nearby base stations, previous research has examined preferred locations for one (or more) new base stations. Using both qualitative and quantitative approaches, Cousin and colleagues (Cousin et al., 2011; Cousin & Siegrist, 2010a, 2010b), showed that people tend to prefer the most distant location when choosing among several locations. In all three studies, a sketch of a fictional town was used to visualize where the base stations would be located. In a pairwise comparison of five possible scenarios (some consisting of several less powerful base stations), the

majority of respondents favored the scenario in which the base station was located furthest from the town center (Cousin & Siegrist, 2010b). Their qualitative study further demonstrated that the incorrect assessment of the relationship between distance and exposure, and thus also the primary source of exposure, strongly influenced location choice (Cousin & Siegrist, 2010a).

Furthermore, studies on acceptance of base stations suggest that installations are typically accepted only at a distance of at least 1 km from the reference point (Freudenstein, Wiedemann, & Brown, 2015). It remains unclear whether lower exposure levels lead to closer locations being accepted (Freudenstein, Wiedemann, & Brown, 2015; Wiedemann et al., 2018).

1.3. Decision making regarding base stations

When choosing between multiple options for base station locations, people weigh several considerations (e.g., distance, exposure, reception, visual characteristics) in a heuristic rather than fully systematic way (Cousin & Siegrist, 2010a; Häring et al., 2024; Kahneman, 2011). We refer to these considerations as *siting factors*, defined as attributes of potential locations that respondents perceive as relevant for their decision. While place attachment explains why residents may value collective and personal environmental goals and highlights the limitations of the NIMBY concept (Devine-Wright, 2009; Devine-Wright & Batel, 2017; Perlaviciute et al., 2018, 2021), multi-attribute utility theory (MAUT; Baron, 1994) describes how multiple siting factors are cognitively weighed against each other. Combining place attachment and MAUT offers a key advantage: place attachment helps identify relevant location attributes and decision-relevant considerations, whereas MAUT provides a framework for how these considerations are weighed and integrated in the decision-making process, ultimately leading to a specific siting decision. Fig. 1 illustrates how the two theories can be integrated into a joint model and how they interrelate in the context of the present study.

1.4. The present studies

Building on the theoretical considerations outlined above, place attachment posits that evaluations of a hypothetical base station

location are shaped by emotional bonds to one's home and surroundings, which can be reflected, for example, in a desire for less exposure, better reception, or visual integrity. MAUT complements this perspective: it provides a conceptual lens for interpreting location choices as the result of trade-offs between multiple siting factors (e.g., distance, visual characteristics, reception, and perceived exposure), without formally modelling utilities. Together, these frameworks guided the design of our studies and informed our interpretation as to why certain locations are perceived as more acceptable or worthy of protection than others.

The present studies have two main objectives: firstly, to examine whether preferences for locations of 4G-plus 5G-capable base station align with earlier findings and secondly, to investigate the factors that may influence the public's location preferences, helping us to understand why certain locations are favored. Notably, most 5G base stations that have been deployed up to now do not look fundamentally different to base stations of earlier mobile communications standards.

Cousin and colleagues (Cousin et al., 2011; Cousin & Siegrist, 2010a, 2010b) investigated public location preferences for base stations in the 2000s in the context of 2G mobile communications technology, which had been rolled out since 1992. The present study differs from their work in six main ways. First, we examine location preferences for the latest mobile communications standards, 4G and 5G. Second, whereas base stations were newly implemented in Cousin et al.'s (2011) scenario, participants in our study were told that the town was already covered with 2G reception and was to be upgraded with a 4G-plus 5G-capable antenna. Third, differently from Cousin and Siegrist (2010b, 2010a) and Cousin et al. (2011), participants were given a reference point by asking them to assume that they lived in a particular house and to choose a location based on this assumption. We did so because we assumed that a person's own living space is ascribed a special value worthy of protection. Drawing on place attachment, we further assumed that decisions would differ depending on whether the reference point is a respondent's own home or the town as a whole, as we would expect associated emotional bonds and place meanings to differ. Fourth, while location preferences have been assessed previously (Cousin et al., 2011; Cousin & Siegrist, 2010a, 2010b), the present study is the first to examine location preferences *and* the reasons for those preferences. In line with MAUT, these reasons are conceptualized as attributes that jointly inform the overall evaluation of a location rather than being considered in

Fig. 1. Theoretical model.

Note. Place attachment forms the foundation of the decision: it gives rise to desires (aims), which are then translated into factors that can be weighed against each other in the decision-making process.

isolation. Fifth, location preferences and their underlying reasons were examined in ten European countries, whereas Cousin and Siegrist focused exclusively on the Swiss population (Cousin et al., 2011; Cousin & Siegrist, 2010a, 2010b). Sixth, the present study differs in its theoretical foundation. While Cousin and colleagues (Cousin et al., 2011; Cousin & Siegrist, 2010a, 2010b) adopted a more applied behavioural perspective, the present study goes beyond describing location preferences by also investigating the underlying reasons. Specifically, it integrates both place attachment and MAUT to account for more intuitive, feeling-based response as well as more deliberate, cognitive evaluations of decision making, thereby allowing for conclusions regarding the applicability of both theories for explaining location preferences for mobile phone base stations.

Since location preferences for base stations have so far only been investigated for 2G-capable base station (Cousin & Siegrist, 2010a, 2010b), the present studies aim to address the question of where members of the public would place a new 4G-plus 5G-capable base station if they had the choice (RQ1). In the theoretical model we propose, this question captures the observable outcome of the decision process.

While exposure characteristics posing potential health risks to mobile phone users have been examined previously (Freudenstein, Wiedemann, & Brown, 2015; Freudenstein, Wiedemann, & Varsier, 2015), it has not yet been analyzed how characteristics such as distance and exposure levels influence location preferences. Therefore, we examine which factors affect the members of the public's choice of location (RQ2). This question directly reflects the MAUT perspective by identifying the attributes that enter the decision process and allows us to assess how different siting factors contribute to observed preferences. Notably, we compare the decision process of people with different location preferences. Finally, since EMF risk perception varies considerably across countries (TNS Opinion & Social, 2010), the present study looks at different countries and investigates how widespread these location preferences and explanations across ten different European countries are (RQ3).

To investigate these questions, we used a sequential mixed methods design, in which qualitative findings are used to inform subsequent quantitative analyses (Clark & Creswell, 2008). Integration occurred at both the design and interpretation stages, with qualitative insights shaping survey construction and hypothesis development, and quantitative results being interpreted in light of the qualitative findings. Both stages were informed by the assumption that siting decisions can be explained both by attitudinal variables (e.g., risk perception), which shape how individuals evaluate certain siting factors (e.g., distance, reception, ...), and by process variables. Process variables are represented by the siting factors, which reflect how multiple attributes are weighed and traded off in the decision-making process in line with MAUT. Study 1, conducted in December 2022, comprised qualitative interviews and focus groups. A key element was an interactive siting task in which participants were asked to choose one of six possible locations for a new 4G-plus 5G-capable base station and give reasons for their choice. Study 2, an international survey, conducted between September and December 2023, comprised a siting task as well. Study 1 addressed RQ1 and RQ2 qualitatively, while Study 2 addressed RQ1, RQ2 and RQ3 quantitatively. The hypotheses tested in Study 2 are introduced after the presentation of the results of Study 1 (3.2. Hypotheses).

2. Study 1 – focus groups

2.1. Material and methods

2.1.1. The sample

Between December 5-7, 2022, we conducted six focus groups ($n = 35$), alongside individual interviews with the same participants, in the cities of Augsburg and Munich and surrounding rural areas (Germany). At the time of data collection, 5G rollout differed across these locations.

Whereas 5G was already implemented in the two cities (group 1 and 2) and most rural areas (group 3, 5, and 6), one village was selected in which 5G was planned but had not yet been initiated (group 4). Participants were recruited via a market research company. The company was instructed to target an equal distribution of men and women, as well as to select people of different ages and with different levels of professional education. Ownership of a 5G-capable mobile phone was also considered in recruitment.

The sample included 18 women and 17 men, who were on average 39 years old (range 18-67 years). 13 participants owned a 5G-capable mobile phone. Group composition is shown in Table 1.

2.1.2. Data acquisition

Individual interviews were conducted by eight trained interviewers, while all focus groups were moderated by the same interviewer. Both the individual interviews and the focus groups were conducted in German and with the same participants. Accordingly, six (in one case five) participants were interviewed individually in parallel before meeting in the focus group. This approach allowed us to capture both individual perspectives and group-level discussion. Moreover, the focus groups enabled an exchange between the participants and therefore better reflect the kinds of discussions that might occur within communities when a new base station is proposed. To ensure that the same topics were discussed in all individual interviews and focus groups, we used (semi-)structured interview guides. We recorded the audio of individual interviews and video-recorded the focus group discussions.

As the siting task was part of a larger study on the perception of 5G, participants had already engaged with issues related to RF-EMF exposure prior to the location choice. For the present analyses, we focus primarily on participants' base station location preferences (derived from the focus groups) and sociodemographic data of the sample (derived from the individual interviews).

2.1.3. Material

We presented participants with a sketch of a village in which a single base station was to be placed (see Fig. 2). The six possible locations were chosen to a) cover different distances (in the village center (sites 2 and 4), on the outskirts (sites 1 and 3), far outside the village (sites 5 and 6)) and b) to include visually distinct antenna types (see Fig. 3), thereby enabling participants to visualize how the base station would appear at each location. While base stations located outside village centers and are anchored to the ground using tower-like structures, base stations sited within village centers usually comprise a pillar to which transmitters are attached. The task itself (exact wording provided in Table 2) was to choose one of six possible locations (shown in Fig. 2) for a new base station, assuming that they live in the house marked with the chimney (near locations 2 and 4). The locations are referred to as follows:

Table 1
Sociodemographic data by focus group.

Group Nr	Recruitment Area	Gender (Age)	Main Occupation	5G phone
1	City (Augsburg)	4 m (20,25,42,56), 2 f (24,53)	3 emp, 3 stud	2
2	City (Munich)	2 m (50,55), 4 f (23,23,23,54)	3 emp, 3 stud	3
3	Countryside	3 m (27,45,61), 3 f (34,41,52)	5 emp, 1 house	3
4	Countryside, area shortly before 5G roll out	3 m (18,18,48), 3 f (35,41,67)	3 emp, 2 stud, 1 ret	0
5	Countryside	2 m (32,38), 3 f (26,47,50)	2 emp, 2 stud, 1 house	2
6	Countryside	3 m (22,53,62), 3 f (22,39,49)	5 emp, 1 ret	3

Note. m = male, f = female, emp = employed, stud = student/trainee, ret = retired, house = housewife/househusband.

Fig. 2. Sketch of a village with six possible locations for a new base station. Participants were told to imagine they live in the house with the chimney (close to site 2 and 4). The sketch at the bottom right shows the revised version for Study 2. © Helene Uhl.

Fig. 3. Visualization of how the base station would look depending on the choice of location. © Helene Uhl Note. The blue-framed base station would be installed on top of a building, the orange-framed one within a village on the ground, and the green-framed base station in the forest, outside the village. The antennas were only presented in Study 1. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

'Location 1 (edge, ground-based)', 'Location 2 (center, ground-based)', 'Location 3 (industrial site)', 'Location 4 (center, rooftop)', 'Location 5 (distant)', and 'Location 6 (most distant)'.

2.1.4. Data analysis

Focus group discussions were transcribed by five persons using the software F4transkript (dr. dresing & pehl GmbH, 2021). A transcription guideline (based on Dresing & Pehl, 2015) was used to ensure a comparable depth of interpretation later on. Coding was guided by deductively derived categories which were supplemented inductively as new themes emerged (following Mayring, 2015). We used MAXQDA (VERBI Software, 2021) to structure the data according to the categories. All transcripts were coded by the same researcher and then checked by a

second researcher. Moreover, the responses of the preferred location for the new base station was analyzed.

2.2. Results

RQ 1: Where would members of the public place a new 4G-plus 5G-capable base station if they had the choice?

Location 3 (industrial site) was chosen most frequently ($n = 16$), followed by Location 6 (most distant, $n = 8$). Location 5 (distant) was chosen five times, Location 4 (center, rooftop) two times and Location 1 (edge, ground-based) one time. No participant expressed a preference for Location 2 (center, ground-based). Three participants were

Table 2

Instructions for the siting task for both the current study (Study 1) and the subsequent international survey (Study 2) for comparison.

Study 1 – Focus Groups	Study 2 – International Survey
<p>Now imagine that in this scenario you live in the house with the chimney. Until now, there was only 2G reception at your place of residence, which means you could write text messages, for example, but otherwise had very limited use of the internet via mobile data. A new base station antenna is now to be erected that will cover the locality with 4G and 5G. So far, however, it is unclear where the base station antenna will be erected. For this purpose, six possible locations have been identified, which are drawn and numbered on the map. Depending on your choice, the appearance of the base station antenna differs. The six possible locations are marked with an X in the drawing.</p>	<p>Now we would like you to put yourself in a situation where a new mobile phone mast will be erected. Imagine that you live in the house circled in red. Six possible locations have been identified for the new mast. They are marked and numbered on the map.</p> <p>For your information: At the moment you have only 2G reception at your home, which means you can call and write text messages, but can only use the internet via mobile data to a very limited extent. With the new mobile phone mast, the village will have 4G and 5G coverage.</p> <p>Please take a moment to look at the entire picture in detail.</p>

undecided.

RQ2: What factors affect members of the public's choice of location?

Aesthetic aspects were mentioned most frequently. Twelve participants across five groups referred to negative visual impacts on the landscape if a base station were built in the woods (e.g., “this completely disrupts nature”, female, 49, countryside, or “with one of the green locations, I would actually lose a little bit of that sense of nature”, female, 23, city), referring to Locations 5 and 6. Also, ten participants across five groups emphasized that the industrial site was already ugly (e.g., “... on the ugly big factory building with its thick chimneys, it's easiest to put the thing on it”, male, 27, countryside) and considered it a suitable site for a base station. Both aspects were given as reasons to place the base station rather than the factory building than in wooded areas.

A second siting approach (discussed in three focus groups, with ten individual responses) was to place the base station as far away as possible (e.g., “it's just the furthest away”, male 18, countryside). In three focus groups each, albeit with fewer individual responses, participants also stated that the highway (three individual responses) and the factory (four individual responses) should also be able to benefit from good mobile internet, and that higher base stations—as at Location 5 and 6—could guarantee better network coverage (four individual responses).

Exposure to EMF was only discussed by three individuals across two groups, making a statement about the influence distance has on exposure. Beliefs differed markedly: one participant assumed that a greater distance would lead to more exposure (“if I build it somewhere at the back of the hill, then it has to radiate more so that the village is covered really well”, male, 55, city), another participant wanted to place the mast as close as possible to the reference point for the same reasons, while a third participant assumed that “the radiation is probably the same everywhere” (male, 56, city). This suggests that beliefs about the influence of distance on exposure are very heterogeneous, but that members of the public also have correct conceptions alongside misconceptions.

2.3. Discussion

Our analysis of the focus groups showed that (semi)-distant locations were generally preferred over closer locations and that visual aspects influenced location preferences. While some participants wanted to protect the forest from being spoiled, the already ugly industrial site was regarded as a good choice. Although the siting approach of placing the

base station as far away as possible is consistent with Cousin and colleagues (Cousin et al., 2011; Cousin & Siegrist, 2010a, 2010b), it was not the dominant approach taken by participants in our study. However, it is worth emphasizing that we also observed some participants following the approach ‘as far away as possible’.

Participants' preference for Location 3 (industrial site) and their reasoning highlights the importance of aesthetic considerations (Betakova et al., 2015; Carlisle et al., 2016; Hermans, 2015). In addition to distance and aesthetic aspects, reception and perceived exposure to RF-EMF appear to be relevant in the public's appraisals of base stations sites. The focus groups showed that alongside a possible selfish element utilitarian considerations are weighed in the decision-making process (cf. Baron, 1994), as seen in their reasoning about network coverage for the highway or the industrial site.

Study 1 provided an exploratory insight into how individuals reason about base station siting decisions and into those considerations that they spontaneously emphasize. These qualitative insights informed the design of Study 2 by identifying key siting factors, refining survey items, and, alongside theory, guiding hypothesis development. Focus group discussions repeatedly highlighted distance, perceived exposure (RF-EMF), reception, and visual appearance as salient decision criteria. Conversely, considerations related to procedural aspects of decision-making were mentioned less frequently and were therefore not operationalized in the survey.

3. Study 2 – International survey

Study 2 followed Study 1 as part of a sequential mixed-methods design, enabling qualitative insights to inform the international survey. The international survey was based on an approximately representative sample, thereby increasing the practical relevance of the findings.

3.1. Introduction

The international survey was conducted in ten European countries (and Japan; however, the Japanese data are not considered here since they were collected at a later point in time) and relied on similar materials to those used in Study 1. Based on a sketch of a fictional village (see Fig. 2) survey respondents were first asked to select one of six possible locations (exact wording see Table 2). Then they were asked to indicate the extent to which reasons most frequently mentioned in Study 1 influenced their decision: *distance* to the reference point, *reception*, exposure to *electromagnetic fields (EMFs)* and *visual appearance*. Fig. 4 shows how these factors were integrated into an overarching model.

The influencing factors can be understood as mediators that also have an effect on the choice of location and being affected by respondents' sociodemographic characteristics or preconceptions.

3.2. Hypotheses

In line with MAUT, the qualitative findings from Study 1 suggested systematic trade-offs between distance-related concerns and technical performance, which motivated the comparative hypotheses tested in Study 2. Statements emphasizing risk avoidance and community protection are consistent with place attachment and informed hypotheses regarding preferences for more distant locations, whereas comments highlighting better reception and visual disturbance informed hypotheses related to centrally located or visually unattractive sites. Place attachment helps explain how different siting factors influence the perceived value of specific locations: for instance, a location may be preferred if reception is better, or a base station may be placed farther away in the belief that exposure decreases with distance, thereby protecting one's own or the community's space. Visual aspects, in particular, play a role in shaping perceptions of a space worthy of protection.

Therefore—drawing from both the literature and our findings from

Fig. 4. Schematic representation of the expected relationship between sociodemographic characteristics and preconceptions, the reasons for the choice of location, and location preferences.

Note. Dotted lines represent paths that were only analyzed exploratively. ‘Other’ was included in the model to check whether the four influencing factors identified reflect the cognitive processes sufficiently well.

Study 1—we hypothesized that participants would tend to follow one of two siting approaches when selecting a location: approach A ‘as far away as possible’, and approach B ‘at the visually most unappealing location’.

Hypothesis 1. More people choose the most distant (H1A) / visually most unappealing (H1B) location than would be expected by chance.

Hypothesis 1 refers to RQ1.

We further assumed that different siting factors would influence location choice in distinct ways:

Hypothesis 2. In general, people consider distance (H2A) and aesthetic aspects (H2B) more strongly in their decision-making than reception and electromagnetic fields (EMFs).

Hypothesis 3. Considerations about distance (H3A) and EMFs (H3B) have a greater (subjectively perceived) influence on the siting decision in people who chose the most distant location than in people who have chosen another location.

Hypothesis 4. Considerations about aesthetic aspects have a greater (subjectively perceived) influence on the siting decision in people who chose the visually most unappealing location than in those who have chosen another location.

Specifically, with regard to the sketch we used, we assumed that Location 3 (industrial site) would most likely be perceived as a compromise of several siting factors—like *distance*, visual *appearance*, reception and electromagnetic fields (EMFs). Accordingly, H5 examines a different aspect of decision-making than H4: while H4 focuses on the influence of aesthetic aspects, H5 evaluates the number of siting factors considered important for Location 3.

Hypothesis 5. For people who choose Location 3, more siting factors are important than for people who choose another location.

Hypotheses 2 to 5 therefore refer to RQ2. All hypotheses were described in a preregistration available on the Open Science Framework: <https://osf.io/hbrc7/overview>. Deviations from the preregistration are listed in Appendix A.

The remaining paths depicted in Fig. 4 were analyzed exploratively (RQ3).

3.3. Material and methods

Detailed information on the study design and questionnaire is available via the Open Science Framework: <https://osf.io/xbk57/overview>.

3.3.1. Data acquisition

The present study relies on data that were collected in Austria, Finland, France, Germany, Greece, Poland, Serbia, Slovenia, Spain, and

the United Kingdom. These countries were selected because 5G deployment was at a different stage across countries (European Commission, 2024) at the time of data collection and because previous research has documented substantial cross-country differences in EMF risk perception (TNS Opinion & Social, 2010).

Data collection occurred in two waves: a soft launch between September and October 2023 and a full launch in December 2023. Approximately 1000 people per country were recruited based on quota combinations for age and gender (interlocking), and region (non-interlocking, based on NUTS-1 (European Commission, 2019); smallest quota: $n = 6$). The survey was administered using Unipark software EFS Survey (Unipark, 2023). Respondents received the survey link from the panel provider and were incentivized by collecting points.

The questionnaire was structured in several blocks and designed to avoid priming positive or negative attitudes towards EMF technologies. Average completion time was 21 min.

3.3.2. Sample

Respondents who did not complete the survey, failed one of the two attention checks, or completed the survey too quickly or too slowly (less than 10 min, more than 60 min; thresholds are based on pre-tests) were immediately screened out and therefore not included in the sample. The final sample comprised 10,358 respondents, with approximately 1000 individuals per country. Respondents were on average 47 years old (range: 16-93). 50.7% identified as female, 48.8% as male and 0.5% as diverse/transgender.

In some cases, not all quotas could be met. To still maintain representativeness in these characteristics, sample weights were applied.

3.3.3. Relevant Data and New Variables

The location choice and the reasons for the choice of location (siting factors) are of particular relevance (see Tables 2 and 3 for exact wording) for the present study. Also, sociodemographic characteristics such as age (categorized; 16-24, 25-34, 35-44, 45-54, 55-64, 65+) and gender (binary; male, female) and attitudinal variables were included. These comprised 5G risk perception, 5G exposure perception, 5G use, acceptance of 5G, and expected impact of 5G (see Table 3).

To test Hypotheses 3 and 5, we computed two new variables. First, rank variables were created to capture the relative importance of the five siting factors. Each of the five rank variables can assume a value between 1 and 5, with higher values indicating higher relative importance. If two or more variables received identical ratings in the original variables, they were assigned the same rank. Second, we calculated a variable reflecting the number of factors that were rated at least moderately (≥ 4) relevant for the location choice (“relevance siting factors”). This variable ranged from 0 (= no factor rated ≥ 4) to 5 (= all factors rated ≥ 4).

Table 3
Variables used in the analyses.

Variable	Question	Response options
Choice of location	“Which location would you prefer for the new 4G/5G mobile phone mast?”	“Location 1: The mobile phone mast is erected on the outskirts of the village and anchored to the ground.”, “Location 2: The mobile phone mast is erected on a nearby square and anchored to the ground.”, “Location 3: The mobile phone mast is erected on the roof of the factory.”, “Location 4: The mobile phone mast is erected on a nearby rooftop of a house.”, “Location 5: The mobile phone mast is erected on a hill near the village and anchored to the ground.”, and “Location 6: The mobile phone mast is erected on a hill far outside the village and anchored to the ground.”
Reasons	“How strongly did the following factors influence your choice of location?” ... “Reception”, “Distance”, Electromagnetic fields (EMFs)”, “Visual appearance”, and “Other”	“1 = no influence at all”, “4 = moderately”, “7 = very strong influence”
Age	Please enter your age.	###
Gender	“Please select your gender identity.”	“Woman”, “Man”, “Transgender”, “Non-binary/non-conforming”, “Other”, and “Prefer not to answer”
Risk perception (RP)	“How serious are the potential health risks for ...”: a) “you personally”; b) “the general public”; and c) “children”, ... “from electromagnetic fields (EMFs) related to the following technologies?”—“5G mobile technologies”, “older mobile technologies (3G/4G)”, “Wi-Fi”, “microwave ovens”, “power lines”, “radio”, and “TV”.	“1 = not at all serious” to “7 = extremely serious”
Exposure perception (EP)	“How much do you think you are exposed to electromagnetic fields (EMFs) from mobile communications devices and mobile phone masts (incl. 5G technology) in your everyday life?”	“1 = not at all” to “7 = to a very high degree”
Use	“To your knowledge, do you use 5G on your mobile phone?”	“yes”, “no”, and “I don't know”
Acceptance	“I am in favor of the expansion of the 5G network.”	“1 = completely disagree” to “7 = completely agree”
Impact	“How do you think the introduction of 5G technology affects”: a) “you personally” and b) “society as a whole”?”	“-3 = very negatively”, “0 = neither negatively nor positively”, “+3 = very positively”

For exploratory analyses, two indices were calculated: a 5G risk perception index based on the three 5G risk perception items ($\alpha = .954$), and an impact index, based on two items ($\alpha = .863$).

3.3.4. Statistical software/analysis

Before starting the analysis, we cleaned and prepared the data using R (R Core Team, 2023). To analyze the data, we used SPSS version 28.0.1.0 (IBM Corp, 2021) and JASP version 0.18.3. (JASP Team, 2024).

To examine whether more people than expected by chance choose the most distant location (Location 6, H1A) or the visually most unappealing location (Location 3, H1B), we conducted a multinomial test. To test whether Locations 3 (industrial site) and 6 (most distant) were each chosen more frequently than Locations 1 (edge, ground-based), 2

(center, ground-based), 4 (center, rooftop), and 5 (distant), we performed eight binomial tests. We adjusted the significance levels to $p < .001$ to avoid alpha inflation.

To test whether the siting factors *distance* (H2A) and *visual appearance* (H2B) influenced respondents’ decision processes more than *reception* and *electromagnetic fields (EMFs)*, we calculated a repeated measures ANOVA. The repeated measures factor had five levels: *distance*, *visual appearance*, *reception*, *electromagnetic fields (EMFs)* and *other*.

Based on the rank variables (see section “3.3.3. Relevant Data and New Variables”), we tested whether *distance* (H3A) and *EMFs* (H3B) were more influential when deciding for Location 6 (most distant) than when deciding for another location by performing a Mann Whitney *U* test. We conducted another Mann Whitney *U* test to test whether people who decided for Location 3 (industrial site) attributed greater influence to *visual appearance* than others (H4).

We used a one-way ANOVA to test whether people who choose Location 3 (industrial site) consider more factors relevant for their decision than people who choose another location (H5). For this reason, we calculated the variable *relevance siting factors* (see section “3.3.3. Relevant Data and New Variables”).

Lastly, we conducted exploratory multiple mediation analyses to further examine why certain locations were preferred. These analyses investigated the effect of sociodemographic characteristics such as age and gender as well as the influence of preconceptions such as risk perception, exposure perception, use of 5G, acceptance and expected impact of 5G on location choice. The analyses included both direct effects of these characteristics and indirect effects via the siting factors *distance*, *EMFs*, *reception* and *visual appearance*. We conducted the analyses for the full sample as well as for each country separately.

Due to the application of weights in some analyses, the sample size can deviate from $n = 10,358$. This discrepancy arises from SPSS’s varying treatment of weights: some procedures disregard weights, while others interpret the weighting variable as a replication weight and round fractional weights to the nearest whole number (IBM Corp, 2024).

We interpret effect sizes according to Lovakov and Agadullina (2021), who empirically derived effect sizes for social psychology (thresholds: small effects: $d = .15/r = .12$; medium effects: $d = .36/r = .24$; large effects: $d = .65/r = .41$).

We conducted a sensitivity power analysis for Study 2. Given the large sample size ($n = 10,358$), the study had 80% power ($\alpha = .05$, two-tailed) to detect very small effects (approximately $d = .05$ for mean differences, $r = .03$ for non-parametric comparisons, and $f = .03$ for ANOVA), indicating high sensitivity to even subtle differences.

3.4. Results

3.4.1. Descriptive statistics

Across all respondents, *distance* ($M = 5.18$, $SD = 1.75$) was considered to have the greatest influence on the decision process, followed by *reception* ($M = 4.65$, $SD = 1.84$) and *electromagnetic fields (EMFs)* ($M = 4.47$, $SD = 2.01$). In contrast, *visual appearance* ($M = 3.80$, $SD = 2.01$) and *other* ($M = 2.94$, $SD = 1.85$) played a considerably smaller role. All five variables correlated significantly with each other ($|r| = .023$, 95%CI [-.04, .00] – .531, 95%CI [.52, .55]), which can be explained by the fact that *distance*, for example, has an influence on exposure, but also on reception and possible visual disturbance effects.

At the country level, *EMFs* emerged as the most influential factor in location choice in all countries except Finland, where *reception* was considered to have the greatest influence. This pattern is consistent with EMF risk perception reported in the Special Eurobarometer (TNS Opinion & Social, 2010): among the countries included in the present study, only 21% of the Finnish population perceived EMFs as a risk, compared to 81% of the Greek population. *EMFs* also showed the greatest cross-national variation, ranging from $M = 3.18$ in Finland to $M = 5.52$ in Greece. By comparison, the perceived influence of *distance* and *reception* varies less across countries, with ranges of .86 (Finland vs.

Greece) and .75 (UK vs. Poland) scale units, respectively. Further descriptive statistics are provided in Table 4.

3.4.2. Location preferences

Across all countries, respondents showed a preference for very distant locations. The most frequently chosen option was Location 6 (53.6%), followed by location 5 (20.2%) and Location 3 (13.00%).

Although respondents from all countries preferred distant sites or the industrial site, the strength of preferences differed markedly between countries. For instance, approval for Location 6 ranged from 42.8% in Austria to 65.3% in Greece. The industrial site (Location 3) ranked third in all analyzed countries except for Austria with cross-country differences of up to 17.2% (Greece vs. Austria). Fig. 5 displays the relative frequency of location choices by country.

A multinomial test (see Table 5) confirmed that the two locations far outside the village (Location 5 and 6) were selected more frequently than expected by chance (i.e. 16.7%), $\chi^2(5) = 11684.95, p < .001, n = 10,358$.

Binomial tests showed that Location 6 (most distant) was chosen

Table 4
Bivariate correlations between factors possible influencing location preferences and mean values of each siting factor.

	Reception	Distance	EMFs	Visual ap.	Other
Reception	4.65 (1.84)				
Distance	.157 [.14, .18]**	5.18 (1.75)			
EMFs	-.023 [-.04, .00]*	.531 [.52, .55]**	4.47 (2.01)		
Visual ap.	.138 [.12, .16]**	.177 [.16, .20]**	.169 [.15, .19]**	3.80 (2.01)	
Other	.082 [.06, .10]**	.127 [.11, .15]**	.217 [.20, .24]**	.407 [.39, .42]**	2.94 (1.85)
Location 1	4.75 (1.76)	4.75 (1.64)	3.93 (1.89)	3.68 (1.98)	2.83 (1.76)
Location 2	5.41 (1.75)	4.67 (1.95)	3.49 (2.06)	3.44 (2.11)	3.07 (1.96)
Location 3	4.83 (1.66)	4.44 (1.62)	3.43 (1.80)	4.05 (2.23)	2.97 (1.82)
Location 4	5.82 (1.60)	5.16 (1.96)	4.11 (2.42)	3.90 (2.28)	3.39 (2.12)
Location 5	5.10 (1.55)	4.88 (1.54)	3.91 (1.89)	3.55 (1.94)	2.65 (1.70)
Location 6	4.32 (1.93)	5.54 (1.75)	5.08 (1.88)	3.86 (2.14)	3.02 (1.88)
Austria	4.43 (1.93)	4.80 (1.88)	4.05 (2.03)	3.68 (2.10)	2.81 (1.75)
Finland	4.99 (1.89)	4.66 (1.81)	3.18 (1.98)	3.19 (2.00)	2.79 (1.74)
France	4.61 (1.77)	5.53 (1.55)	4.89 (1.83)	4.24 (2.02)	3.16 (1.92)
Germany	4.49 (1.85)	5.04 (1.69)	4.14 (1.96)	3.64 (2.04)	2.87 (1.73)
Greece	4.61 (1.82)	5.52 (1.67)	5.30 (1.77)	4.03 (2.12)	2.75 (1.89)
Poland	5.01 (1.65)	5.34 (1.59)	4.67 (1.92)	4.02 (2.01)	2.95 (1.90)
Serbia	4.71 (1.88)	5.04 (1.86)	4.68 (1.93)	3.09 (2.04)	2.83 (1.85)
Slovenia	4.89 (1.74)	5.30 (1.69)	4.94 (1.80)	3.84 (2.09)	3.20 (1.96)
Spain	4.45 (1.83)	5.50 (1.66)	4.96 (1.90)	4.14 (2.01)	3.26 (1.87)
UK	4.26 (1.92)	5.03 (1.78)	3.93 (2.06)	4.08 (2.01)	2.75 (1.78)

Note. The upper part of the table shows the mean values and standard deviations as well as the correlations including 95% CIs between the siting factors for the entire sample. The lower part of the table shows the mean values and standard deviations for each location and country. Significance: *p ≤ .05, **p < .001, n.s. = not significant. N = 10,066.

significantly more frequently than Location 1, 2, 4, and 5 (all p < .001; see Supplementary Table 1). In contrast, Location 3 (industrial site) was chosen more frequently only when compared to Location 1, 2, and 4, but not more frequently than Location 5 (all p < .001; see Supplementary Table 1). Results pertaining to Hypothesis 1 show that the location farthest away (Location 6) received the greatest approval, whereas the approval for the visually most unappealing location (Location 3) was—with two exceptions, Austria (23.5%) and Germany (18.5%)—no greater than would be expected by chance.

3.4.3. Influence attributed to siting factors

A repeated measures ANOVA (Huynh-Feldt corrected) showed that location preferences were affected to varying degrees by the five siting factors ($F(3.50,31922.160) = 2725.536, p < .001, \eta^2 = .204, n = 10,615$). Distance was rated as significantly more influential than reception and EMFs (small to medium effects). This result supports H2A. Visual appearance was rated less influential than reception and EMFs. This finding contradicts H2B, which predicted a stronger role for visual aspects. Details on the pairwise comparisons can be found in Supplementary Table 2.

Nonparametric analyses (for details see Supplementary Table 3) showed that respondents preferring the most distant site (Location 6) assigned significantly greater importance to both distance and electromagnetic fields (EMFs) than respondents choosing another location, supporting Hypothesis 3.

Conversely, respondents selecting the industrial site (Location 3) attributed significantly higher importance to visual appearance than those choosing other locations, albeit with a small effect size (for details see Supplementary Table 3), thus supporting Hypothesis 4.

A Welch ANOVA indicated significant differences between the locations in the number of siting factors considered at least moderately relevant to the decision ($F(5,1304.942) = 13.531, p < .001, \eta^2 = .007, 95\%CI [.00, .01], n = 10,066$). However, significant differences were observed only between Location 3 (industrial site) and Location 6 (most distant). Since respondents who chose Location 6 considered on average more siting factors to be relevant than those who chose Location 3, Hypothesis 5 was not supported (for results of the post hoc test see Supplementary Table 3).

The results of the hypothesis tests are summarized in Table 6.

3.4.4. Exploratory mediation analyses

For reasons of readability, only the observed main patterns are reported below; coefficients, confidence intervals and significance levels are provided in Supplementary Table 4.

Model 1—choice of location 3 (industrial site). In the total sample, the choice of Location 3 was negatively associated with distance and EMFs and positively associated with reception and visual appearance (see Fig. 6). Older people were less likely to choose Location 3, whereas men were more likely to do so. Risk perception and impact reduced the likelihood of choosing Location 3, while a higher exposure perception increased it.

Several sociodemographic and attitudinal effects were partially mediated by siting factors. In particular, effects of age, gender, risk perception, exposure perception, and impact were partially mediated by distance, EMFs, and visual appearance.

Complete mediations were found for use and acceptance. While use significantly affected the choice of Location 3 via EMFs and reception, acceptance had an indirect effect via EMFs, reception and visual appearance. In all five cases, the associations were positive.

Country-level analyses indicate that the role of mediators varied across national contexts (see Supplementary Table 4). In most countries (Austria, Finland, France, Germany, Poland, Serbia, and Slovenia), respondents who attached more importance to distance were less likely to decide for Location 3. EMFs showed a consistently negative association with the choice of Location 3 across countries, except Serbia. In contrast,

Fig. 5. Relative distribution of location preferences by country.

Table 5
Location preferences (absolute numbers) by country.

	Location 1	Location 2	Location 3	Location 4	Location 5	Location 6
Austria	58	24	234	26	236	433
Finland	56	33	118	36	318	448
France	55	14	129	9	227	573
Germany	71	24	182	36	226	469
Greece	53	19	60	39	177	655
Poland	80	32	132	25	213	520
Serbia	48	33	74	19	189	639
Slovenia	39	31	128	77	197	539
Spain	91	24	94	30	165	604
United Kingdom	78	39	155	16	193	528
Countries combined						
Expected (chance)	1726	1726	1726	1726	1726	1726
Observed	645	289	1360	322	2193	5549

Note. The upper part of the table shows how often a location was chosen depending on the country. The lower part of the table shows the actual frequency and the expected frequency for the choice of each location based on chance.

visual appearance increased the likelihood of choosing Location 3 in several Western and Northern European countries (Austria, Finland, France, Slovenia, and the UK). The importance of reception was positively associated with the choice of Location 3 primarily in Central, Southern, and Eastern European countries (Germany, Greece, Poland, Serbia, Spain, and the UK).

Model 2—choice of Location 6 (most distant). In contrast, the choice of the most distant location was positively associated with distance and EMFs, and negatively associated with reception (see Fig. 6).

Men were more likely to choose Location 6, while a higher acceptance of 5G reduced its likelihood. Risk perception was positively associated with the decision in favor of Location 6. These effects were partly mediated by distance, EMFs and reception. The effect of age was partially mediated by distance and EMFs. Gender had an indirect effect on the choice of Location 6 via distance, EMFs and reception. Risk perception had an indirect effect via distance and EMFs. Acceptance indirectly affected the choice of Location 6 negatively via EMFs and reception.

Full mediations were found for exposure perception, use and impact, all of which influenced the choice of Location 6 through combinations of distance, EMFs and reception.

Similarly to model 1, most of the significant paths observed in the total sample were significant in all/most of the ten countries (see Supplementary Table 4). While there was a positive association between distance (all countries except Greece) and EMFs (all countries) and the choice of Location 6, a consistent negative association was found between reception and a preference for the most distant location. Notably, the effect of visual appearance varied by country: while non-significant in the total sample, it was positively associated with choosing Location 6 in Germany, Serbia and Spain, but negatively associated in Slovenia and the UK.

Overall, the mediation analyses indicate that distance, EMFs, and reception play distinct and location-specific mediating roles, and that their influence varies across national contexts.

3.5. Discussion

Based on our qualitative Study 1, we assumed that the two identified approaches of location choices would also be dominant in the international survey. Specifically, we expected that most respondents would either follow approach A ‘as far away as possible’ and choose Location 6

Table 6
Results of the hypothesis tests.

Hypothesis	Evaluation
H1A: More people choose the most distant location than would be expected by chance.	Supported
H1B: More people choose the visually most unappealing location than would be expected by chance.	Partially supported
H2A: In general, people consider distance more strongly in their decision-making than reception and electromagnetic fields (EMFs).	Supported
H2B: In general, people consider aesthetic aspects more strongly in their decision-making than reception and electromagnetic fields (EMFs).	Not supported
H3A: Considerations about distance have a greater (subjectively perceived) influence on the siting decision in people who chose the most distant location than in people who have chosen another location.	Supported
H3B: Considerations about EMF have a greater (subjectively perceived) influence on the siting decision in people who chose the most distant location than in people who have chosen another location.	Supported
H4: Considerations about aesthetic aspects have a greater (subjectively perceived) influence on the siting decision in people who chose the visually most unappealing location than in those who have chosen another location.	Supported
H5: For people who choose Location 3 more siting factors are important than for people who choose another location.	Not supported

(most distant) or follow approach B ‘at the most visually unappealing location’ and choose Location 3 (industrial site).

In Study 2, we found that more people than expected by chance chose Location 6 (Hypothesis 1A supported). This was observed in all ten countries, with proportions ranging from 42.8% in Austria to 65.3% in Greece. Possible explanations for this between-country variation include differences in risk perception as well as differing relationships to nature (cf. Siegrist & Berthold, 2024) and technology.

Regarding the influence respondents attributed to the siting factors, we found that *distance* and *EMFs* exerted a stronger influence than *reception* and *visual appearance* on the choice of Location 6 (most distant, supporting Hypothesis 3). These effects remained significant when additional predictors such as risk perception and sociodemographic variables were included in exploratory mediation analysis, providing evidence for their incremental validity.

Both higher age and higher perceived risk of 5G increased the likelihood of choosing Location 6 (most distant), corresponding to approach A. While *age* showed a comparably large direct effect on the choice of Location 6, *risk perception* primarily affected the choice of Location 6 mediated through *EMFs*, but also directly and mediated by the influence

of *distance* (both smaller than the indirect effect via *EMFs*). These findings indicate that higher *EMF risk perception* leads individuals to choose the most distant location, making approach A more relevant for those who perceive greater risks.

Although not hypothesized, respondents who attributed greater influence to *reception* were less likely to choose Location 6 (most distant). This effect exceeded that of *EMFs*. Gender indirectly affected the choice of Location 6 via *reception*, with men more likely than women to attribute influence to *reception*. Additionally, those who expressed higher acceptance of 5G were more likely to consider *reception* influential.

In summary, we found strong support for approach A, both in our hypothesis tests and in our exploratory mediation analyses. Approach A emerged as the dominant approach in all ten countries analyzed.

Contrary to expectations derived from qualitative Study 1, we found less evidence for the relevance of approach B in analyses of the international survey. The hypothesis that Location 3 (industrial site) would be chosen more frequently than expected by chance was supported only in Austria and Germany (partial support for Hypothesis 1B). Notably, Germany was also the context of Study 1, suggesting that visually motivated siting strategies may be more salient in German-speaking countries (cf. Siegrist & Berthold, 2024). *Visual appearance* exerted a greater influence on the choice of Location 3 than on other locations, supporting Hypothesis 4. Thus, although the results indicate that Location 3 (industrial site) was chosen far less often than Location 6 (most distant) or 5 (distant), the influence of *visual appearance* on the choice of Location 3 suggests that the expected cognitive processes underlying approach B are present.

The choice of Location 3 (industrial site) was also influenced directly by *age* and—directly and indirectly—*risk perception*. In contrast to Location 6, increasing *age* reduced the likelihood of choosing the industrial site. People with a higher *risk perception*—partly mediated by the influence attributed to *EMFs*—also tend to decide against Location 3.

Based on qualitative Study 1, we expected respondents choosing Location 3 to consider a broader range of siting factors at least moderately influential compared to other locations (Hypothesis 5). This Hypothesis was not supported. The multiple mediation analyses revealed that higher attributed influence of *EMFs* and *distance* was associated with the choice of Location 3, with higher values for both factors being related to a lower likelihood of choosing Location 3. This finding is partially attributional to the fact that Location 3 was tested against all other locations—including Location 6 (most distant), where a higher influence of *distance* and *EMFs* tended to lead to the choice of location. Moreover, mean values for *distance* and *EMFs* were lower at Location 3 than at all other locations.

A preference for the industrial site may further be understood

Fig. 6. Influence of mediators on the choice of Location 3 and 6.

Note: Unstandardized coefficient *b*; a positive value means that a higher value of the respective siting factor makes Location 3/6 more likely to be chosen, while a negative value means that a higher value of the siting factor makes Location 3/6 less likely to be chosen.; significance: ***p* < .001.

through the representativeness heuristic (Tversky & Kahneman, 1974). Industrial areas are commonly associated with technical infrastructure, which may make additional installations appear more fitting in this context. Consequently, considerations about *distance* and *EMFs* may be less salient at the industrial sites than at residential or close to nature locations, as the surrounding land use already signals that such infrastructure is appropriate.

In general, we expected that *distance* and *visual appearance* would have a greater impact on people's decisions than *reception* and *EMFs* (Hypothesis 2). While the dominance of *distance* was indeed the most influential factor when looking at the influence attributed to the siting factors independently of location choice and other variables, our exploratory multiple mediation analyses showed that *distance* does not have decisively determined the choice of either Location 3 (industrial site) or 6 (most distant). This pattern aligns with the mean values attributed to the siting factors depending on location choice. These results may not be generalizable to expert populations, whose evaluations of RF-EMF and distance would likely differ due to more accurate knowledge of exposure conditions.

Beyond hypothesis-driven findings, several additional results are relevant for base station siting preferences more generally. All siting factors correlated significantly, with the strongest correlation between *distance* and *EMFs*. This suggests that *distance* often serves as a cognitive proxy for exposure reduction, and that considerations about *EMFs* and *reception*, both logically related to *distance*, shape how *distance* itself is evaluated. *Distance*, *EMFs* and *reception* also had a significant effect on the choice of both Locations 3 (industrial site) and 6 (most distant).

While *visual appearance* did not significantly affect the choice of Location 6 (most distant) in the total sample, country-level analyses revealed both positive (Germany, Serbia, Spain) and negative effects (Slovenia, UK). These divergent patterns may reflect differences in how landscapes are perceived and valued in different national contexts. In some countries, visual intrusion into natural environments may activate stronger preservation motives, whereas in others, the same location may be perceived as comparatively unobtrusive or less salient.

The exploratory mediation analyses also revealed differences among countries. While the siting factors themselves were evaluated differently depending on the country, attitudinal characteristics such as risk perception influenced this evaluation as well. We found a significant positive relationship between *risk perception* and the attributed influence of the siting factors *distance* and *EMFs* in all ten countries, but with varying degrees of influence. Taking the UK as an example, the influence attributed to *EMFs* is far below the total sample average (UK: $M = 3.94$, total sample: $M = 4.47$), but the influence *risk perception* has on the assessment of *EMFs* is far above average (UK: $b = .75$, total sample: $b = .585$). This shows not only that the degree of influence of individual siting factors differs between countries, but also that the influence of attitudinal variables on the assessment of siting factors varies depending on country. Such cross-national differences align with Eurobarometer findings, which indicate substantial variation across European countries in perception of health risks related to electromagnetic fields (TNS Opinion & Social, 2010).

4. General discussion

This paper examined public preferences regarding the siting of 4G-capable 5G-capable base stations, focusing on both location preferences and the underlying reasons for these preferences. To this end, we conducted a 'siting task' in two complementary studies—a qualitative and a quantitative one—in which participants selected one of six hypothetical locations and subsequently evaluated the factors influencing their decision. The joint display (Supplementary Table 5), a mixed-methods table that juxtaposes qualitative findings from Study 1 with quantitative results from Study 2, illustrates how qualitative insights from Study 1 informed and contextualize the quantitative patterns observed in Study 2. By integrating and combining place attachment and MAUT into

a joint model, we were also able to move beyond a primarily descriptive account of distance-based preferences and to provide a theoretically grounded explanation of both where people prefer infrastructure to be located and why these preferences emerge.

Investigations into *where* people would locate a new base station (RQ1) revealed a preference for locations that correspond to the observed approaches for location choice: approach A ('as far away as possible') and approach B ('at the visually most unappealing location'). In Study 1 the majority of participants favored approach B, whereas in Study 2, approach A dominated, with 53.6% choosing the most distant location. These findings align with earlier studies on 2G (Cousin et al., 2011; Cousin & Siegrist, 2010a, 2010b), suggesting continuity in public siting preferences across generations of mobile technology. Considered from a place attachment perspective, the observed siting behaviour provides support for the assumption that places perceived as potentially worthy of protection tend to be avoided as potential sites for a base station. This applies particularly to one's own home, but in some cases also to more nature-oriented locations.

Regarding *why* people prefer certain locations (RQ2), different factors dominated location choices depending on the nature of the study. Visual aspects were particularly salient in the focus group setting of Study 1, whereas *distance* was rated as the most influential factor in Study 2. These differences can be explained not only by affective activation caused by the materials used, but also by design-related factors. In Study 1, small antenna images guided participants' attention more strongly towards visual aspects, while in Study 2, antenna characteristics were only addressed verbally. According to dual coding theory (Paivio, 1991), verbal and nonverbal stimuli are processed differently, which may explain why *visual appearance* did not exert the expected influence in Study 2 and why respondents tended to choose the more distant locations. Other explanations include group pressure and social desirability effects in the qualitative setting. Participants may have been aware that the most distant location was unlikely to be the technically most feasible choice in practice, although they might prefer it. In Study 1, participants may also have sought to avoid contradicting their previously expressed positive basic attitude towards mobile communications or technological progress, thus avoiding a perceived value-action gap. In Study 2, although respondents on average indicated that *distance* had the strongest influence, *distance* was not the best predictor of location choices. Considerations about *EMFs* and *reception* proved to be better predictors, as they depend on *distance* but are more specific. The observed prioritization of *distance* and *EMFs* in the survey, compared with the emphasis on visual appearance in the qualitative study, illustrates the cognitive weighing of multiple factors, consistent with the MAUT framework. Respondents evaluate several siting factors simultaneously rather than rejecting a location solely on a 'not in my backyard' basis.

This pattern supports the assumption of MAUT, which posits that individuals integrate multiple attributes into an overall evaluation rather than relying on a single dominant criterion. Extending this perspective, our findings demonstrate not only how different attributes (e.g., *EMFs*, *reception*, *visual appearance*) vary in their relative importance, but also how these attributes are linked to underlying attitudinal variables within a mediation framework. In this context, the siting factors can be understood as process variables that capture how attributes are weighed and traded off, while attitudinal variables (e.g., *risk perception*) shape how the siting factors themselves are evaluated. By jointly examining these two components, we provide deeper insights into the underlying decision mechanisms and explicitly model how evaluations are translated into decisions through the weighing and integration of multiple attributes, thereby complementing research that has often relied on place attachment, without explicitly modelling attribute trade-offs. Importantly, the qualitative study relied solely on data from Germany, but hypotheses were formulated for all ten countries included in the international survey. Exploratory analyses allowed for cross-country comparisons (RQ3), revealing that *visual appearance*

exerted opposite effects depending on the country and location choice. Only in Germany and Austria the location on the factory building was chosen more frequently than expected by chance. Consequently, if the qualitative study had included one of the eight countries where the tendency towards the most distant location was stronger, our hypotheses might have been slightly different.

From a theoretical standpoint, these cross-country differences suggest that the weighing of siting factors, as described by MAUT, is context-dependent and may be influenced by cultural or societal factors. At the same time, the variability in preferences indicates that place attachment cannot be readily generalized across contexts but is shaped by culturally specific meanings attributed to different types of landscapes and built environments.

Beyond siting factors, some demographic variables showed significant associations with location preferences. Although gender differences in technology-related risk perception and acceptance have been reported, their interpretation remains contested. Critical scholarship cautions against essentialist explanations and emphasizes the role of social roles, norms, and power relations in shaping reported differences (e.g., Faulkner, 2001). Accordingly, we treated gender as a control variable and report observed effects descriptively without causal interpretation.

Finally, our mixed methods approach demonstrated that location preferences are not solely about *distance*. Even though *distance* has a major influence on location preferences, misconceptions around the relationship between exposure and distance may influence location choice (cf. Cousin & Siegrist, 2010a). Both qualitative and quantitative studies also emphasized that *visual appearance* plays a role, albeit not the dominant one, in perceptions of base stations (cf. Dohle et al., 2010) and siting preferences (cf. Hermans, 2015).

The present studies not only provide insights into the public's location preferences for base stations but also demonstrate that the NIMBY concept falls short of describing the reasons for such preferences. Although distance effects could superficially resemble NIMBY reasoning, preferences are shaped by a combination of *EMFs*, *reception*, and *visual appearance*, indicating a more nuanced, multi-attribute evaluation process. MAUT (Baron, 1994) and place attachment (Devine-Wright, 2009) thus offer psychological explanations for rejection that go beyond a purported selfishness.

Although procedural justice was not directly examined in the present studies, it represents a relevant motivational pathway within the broader place attachment framework. Perceptions of fairness and transparency are likely to shape cognitive evaluations such as trust, risk perception, and acceptance, which are central to location preferences. From this perspective, opposition may arise not only from concerns about physical landscape change (e.g., visual intrusion or exposure), but also from perceived threats to shared meanings, local identity, or social relations tied to place. By focusing on cognitive determinants, the present studies therefore capture evaluations that may partly reflect perceived procedural fairness. Future research could build on these findings by explicitly examining how procedural fairness interacts with cognitive and affective siting evaluations.

Future research should further develop the integration of place attachment and MAUT by examining how place-based meanings shape the selection and weighing of decision attributes in different contexts. Additionally, cross-cultural research could systematically investigate how societal context moderates both place attachment processes and multi-attribute decision-making, thereby refining the theoretical understanding of infrastructure acceptance beyond single-country settings. Moreover, different decision-making models could be used to describe the base station location process, e.g. by models that describe heuristic decision-making (e.g., Gigerenzer & Goldstein, 1996). The value of MAUT and competing decision-making could then be compared for the specific case of infrastructure decision-making.

4.1. Limitations

One limitation of our quantitative approach is that the results require a meaningful interpretation of the decision-making process, which may not reflect the same depth as decision-making processes verbalized in qualitative studies.

Another limitation that persists in the quantitative setting concerns the limited number of possible siting factors that were surveyed. Due to the large sample of 10,358 people, we refrained from openly asking about other possible factors. However, the fact that *other* was assigned the least influence suggests that the selection we made likely covered the most important factors.

The surveyed siting factors also leave room for interpretation. While in the focus groups, for example, the already visually unattractive industrial site was mentioned as a reason for location choice, and nature as a space worthy of protection was also emphasized, *visual appearance* was intended to cover both reasoning patterns. However, this does not allow differentiation of the underlying thought processes.

As the international survey was conducted in ten countries and is therefore available in nine languages, minor differences due to linguistic discrepancies, which might influence how a question is interpreted, cannot be ruled out. Additionally, social desirability bias cannot be ruled out. For instance, participants might not genuinely consider alternative explanations or disclose the actual reasons for rejecting nearby locations. Instead, motivated reasoning (Kunda, 1990) could lead them to construct and communicate socially acceptable justifications to avoid being classified as NIMBY.

Another limitation is that the participants in both the qualitative and quantitative studies had already been confronted with the topic of 5G and exposure prior to the siting task. This is because location preferences were measured as part of larger studies on the perception of 5G. Even if the participants were not informed about existing (mis)conceptions as part of the studies, their location preferences were presumably not completely detached from prior exposure to the topic of exposure.

Although every effort was made to design a survey representative of the general population in terms of age, gender, and region, participating panel survey respondents may not be fully representative of the wider population in terms of their behaviours, opinions, or knowledge of technical issues, etc. due to their motivations for taking part in reward-based panel surveys.

4.2. Conclusions

The current paper provides insights into where the public would place base stations if given the choice, and why certain location preferences emerge. Two high frequency siting approaches were identified: approach A 'as far away as possible' and approach B 'at the visually most unappealing location'. While approach B was preferred in focus group Study 1, approach A was followed by the majority of respondents in the international survey, (Study 2) indicating a preference for more distant base station locations. We found that, depending on the approach, the influence of the recorded siting factors varied. Approach A was associated with a greater influence of *distance* and *EMFs*, whereas *visual appearance* played a more important role for those following approach B. While it has not yet been investigated which siting factors influence the choice of location for base stations, studies on 2G already suggested that distant locations are favored (Cousin & Siegrist, 2010a, 2010b). A similar pattern was observed for 4G/5G, with our qualitative and quantitative studies indicating that, in addition to distant locations, visually unappealing sites are preferred over more central locations in a town, for example. Since the most distant location is usually not the technically most feasible solution, good science and risk communication could help to improve the public's understanding of how mobile communications work. This, in turn, could help overcome misconceptions and potentially reduce controversies about base station siting, alongside other factors not explored here such as procedural justice concerns.

Both studies have received independent ethical approval from the Ethics Committee of the IU International University of Applied Sciences.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Sarah C. Link: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Leanne Martin:** Writing – review & editing, Conceptualization. **James Grellier:** Writing – review & editing, Funding acquisition, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Marie Eggeling-Böcker:** Writing – review & editing, Conceptualization. **Ferdinand Abacioglu:** Writing – review & editing, Conceptualization. **Carolin Schulz:** Writing – review & editing, Conceptualization. **Nina Vaupotic:** Writing – review & editing, Conceptualization. **Mathew P. White:** Writing – review & editing, Conceptualization. **Christoph Boehmert:** Writing – review & editing, Funding acquisition, Data curation, Conceptualization.

Funding

This work was conducted as part of the SEAWave and GOLIAT projects, which received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreements No 101057622 and No 101057262, respectively, and from the UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) under the UK government's Horizon Europe funding guarantee [grant number 10040206] as part of Horizon Europe [HORIZON-HLTH-2021-ENVHLTH-02] under grant agreement number [101057262].

Declaration of interests

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests:

Christoph Boehmert reports financial support was provided by the European Union. James Grellier reports financial support was provided by the European Union and UK Research and Innovation. Given Matthew Whites role as an Associated Editor, he had no involvement in the peer review of this article and had no access to information regarding its peer review. Full responsibility for the editorial process for this article was delegated to another journal editor. If there are other authors, they declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgements

The present study was conducted as part of the HORIZON EUROPE projects "SEAWave" ("scientific-based exposure and risk assessment of radiofrequency and mm-wave systems from children to elderly (5G and beyond)") and "GOLIAT" ("exposure, causal effects, and risk perception through citizen engagement"). We would like to thank our project partners for their valuable support by checking the translations and (pre)testing the questionnaire in their countries. Open access funding enabled and organized by Project DEAL.

Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvp.2026.103070>.

References

Baron, J. (1994). *Thinking and deciding* (2nd ed.). Cambridge University Press.
Betakova, V., Vojar, J., & Sklenicka, P. (2015). Wind turbines location: How many and how far? *Applied Energy*, 151, 23–31. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2015.04.060>

Boehmert, C. A. (2018). The public's reactions to precaution—on the effects of health recommendations regarding wireless communication technologies. <https://doi.org/10.5445/IR/1000086845>.

Carlisle, J. E., Solan, D., Kane, S. L., & Joe, J. (2016). Utility-scale solar and public attitudes toward siting: A critical examination of proximity. *Land Use Policy*, 58, 491–501. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landusepol.2016.08.006>

Claassen, L., Bostrom, A., & Timmermans, D. R. M. (2014). Focal points for improving communications about electromagnetic fields and health: A mental models approach. *Journal of Risk Research*, 19(2), 246–269. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13669877.2014.961519>

Clark, V. L. P., & Creswell, J. W. (2008). *The mixed methods reader*. Sage.

Cousin, M., Dohle, S., & Siegrist, M. (2011). The impact of specific information provision on base station siting preferences. *Journal of Risk Research*, 14(6), 703–715. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13669877.2011.553732>

Cousin, M., & Siegrist, M. (2010a). Risk perception of mobile communication: A mental models approach. *Journal of Risk Research*, 13(5), 599–620. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13669870903236751>

Cousin, M., & Siegrist, M. (2010b). The public's knowledge of mobile communication and its influence on base station siting preferences. *Health, Risk & Society*, 12(3), 231–250. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13698571003710332>

Dashtipour, K., Taylor, W., Ansari, S., Gogate, M., Zahid, A., Sambo, Y., Hussain, A., Abbasi, Q. H., & Imran, M. A. (2021). Public perception of the fifth generation of cellular networks (5G) on social media. *Frontiers in Big Data*, 4. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fdata.2021.640868>

Devine-Wright, P. (2009). Rethinking NIMBYism: The role of place attachment and place identity in explaining place-protective action. *Journal of Community & Applied Social Psychology*, 19(6), 426–441. <https://doi.org/10.1002/casp.1004>

Devine-Wright, P. (2011). Place attachment and public acceptance of renewable energy: A tidal energy case study. *Journal of Environmental Psychology*, 31(4), 336–343. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvp.2011.07.001>

Devine-Wright, P., & Batel, S. (2017). My neighbourhood, my country or my planet? The influence of multiple place attachments and climate change concern on social acceptance of energy infrastructure. *Global Environmental Change*, 47, 110–120. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gloenvcha.2017.08.003>

Dilkova-Gnoyke, N., Jerković, T., Meyer, M., Renner, S., Wachenfeld-Schell, A., & Wieners-Schlupkoth, S. (2022). Sichtweisen der Bevölkerung auf den 5G-Mobilfunkstandard und dessen kommunikative Darstellung-Vorhaben 3620582471. *Bundesamt für Strahlenschutz (BfS)*. <https://doris.bfs.de/jspui/handle/urn:nbn:de:0221-2022041132225>.

Dohle, S., Keller, C., & Siegrist, M. (2010). Conjoint measurement of base station siting preferences. *Human and Ecological Risk Assessment: An International Journal*, 16(4), 825–836. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10807039.2010.501250>

dr dresing, & pehl GmbH. (2021). F4transkript (Version 7) [computer software]. <https://www.audiotranskription.de/en/f4transkript/>.

Dresing, T., & Pehl, T. (2015). *Praxisbuch Interview, Transkription & Analyse: Anleitungen und Regelsysteme für qualitative Forschung* (6th ed.). dr dresing & pehl GmbH.

European Commission. (2024). 5G observatory biannual report of June 2024 (Situation as of 31 March 2024) study on "European 5G Observatory phase III" (CNECT/2021/OP/0008). <https://www.emf-portal.org/en/article/55343>.

Faulkner, W. (2001). The technology question in feminism: A view from feminist technology studies. *Women's Studies International Forum*, 24(1), 79–95. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0277-5395\(00\)00166-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0277-5395(00)00166-7)

Freudenstein, F., Wiedemann, P. M., & Brown, T. W. C. (2015). Exposure perception as a key indicator of risk perception and acceptance of sources of radio frequency electromagnetic fields. *Journal of Environmental and Public Health*, 2015, Article 198272. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2015/198272>

Freudenstein, F., Wiedemann, P. M., & Varsier, N. (2015). Exposure knowledge and risk perception of RF EMF. *Frontiers in Public Health*, 2, 289. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpubh.2014.00289>

Gigerenzer, G., & Goldstein, D. G. (1996). Reasoning the fast and frugal way: Models of bounded rationality. *Psychological Review*, 103(4), 650–669. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0033-295X.103.4.650>

Goette, S., & Ludewig, Y. (2019). Welchen Stellenwert haben Magnetfelder in der öffentlichen Wahrnehmung des Stromnetzausbaus? Eine deutschlandweite Befragung - Vorhaben 3618S82460. *Bundesamt für Strahlenschutz (BfS)*. <https://doris.bfs.de/jspui/handle/urn:nbn:de:0221-2019121120809>.

Goette, S., & Ludewig, Y. (2024). Welchen Stellenwert haben Magnetfelder in der öffentlichen Wahrnehmung des Stromnetzausbaus? Eine deutschlandweite Befragung II - Vorhaben 3621SNA103. *Bundesamt für Strahlenschutz (BfS)*. <https://doris.bfs.de/jspui/handle/urn:nbn:de:0221-2024062644668>.

Häring, C., Jerković, T., Maier, L., Renner, S., Wachenfeld-Schell, A., & Wieners-Schlupkoth, S. (2024). Was denkt Deutschland über Strahlung? Umfrage 2024 : Abschlussbericht Vorhaben 3623S72213. *Bundesamt für Strahlenschutz (BfS)*. <https://doris.bfs.de/jspui/handle/urn:nbn:de:0221-2024121149061>.

Hermans, M. A. (2015). *Engaging with risks: Citizens, science and policy in mobile phone mast siting controversies*. Maastricht University]. <https://doi.org/10.26481/dis.20150206mh>

Herrera-Contreras, A. A., Sánchez-Delacruz, E., & Meza-Ruiz, I. V. (2020). Twitter opinion analysis about topic 5G technology. In M. Botto-Tobar, M. Zambrano Vizuete, P. Torres-Carrión, S. Montes León, G. Pizarro Vásquez, & B. Durakovic (Eds.), *Applied technologies* (pp. 191–203). Springer International Publishing. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-42517-3_15.

IARC. (2013). Non-ionizing radiation, part 2: Radiofrequency electromagnetic fields. <https://publications.iarc.fr/Book-And-Report-Series/Iarc-Monographs-On-The-Identification-Of-Carcinogenic-Hazards-To-Humans/Non-ionizing-Radiation-Part-2-Radiation-Frequency-Electromagnetic-Fields-2013>.

- IBM Corp. (2021). *IBM SPSS Statistics for Windows (Version 28.0.1.0)* [Computer software]. IBM Corp.
- IBM Corp. (2024). Weight cases. <https://www.ibm.com/docs/en/spss-statistics/saas?to pic=transformations-weight-cases>.
- International Commission on Non-Ionizing Radiation Protection. (2009). ICNIRP statement on the “Guidelines for limiting exposure to time-varying electric, magnetic, and electromagnetic fields (up to 300 GHz).”. *Health Physics*, 97(3), 257. <https://doi.org/10.1097/HP.0b013e3181aff9db>
- JASP Team. (2024). *JASP (Version 0.18.3)* [Computer software].
- Kahneman, D. (2011). *Thinking, fast and slow*. macmillan.
- Keystone-SDA. (2019). *Several thousand protest against 5G in Swiss capital*. SWI Swissinfo. Ch. https://www.swissinfo.ch/eng/society/radiation-fears_several-thousand-protest-against-5g-in-swiss-capital/45246224.
- Kunda, Z. (1990). The case for motivated reasoning. *Psychological Bulletin*, 108(3), 480.
- Lienert, P., Sütterlin, B., & Siegrist, M. (2017). The influence of high-voltage power lines on the feelings evoked by different Swiss surroundings. *Energy Research & Social Science*, 23, 46–59. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2016.11.010>
- Link, S. C., Eggeling, M., Abacioglu, F., & Boehmert, C. (2025). Affective evaluation and exposure perception of everyday mobile phone usage situations. *Risk Analysis*, 5(45), 996–1008. <https://doi.org/10.1111/risa.17641>
- Lovakov, A., & Agadullina, E. R. (2021). Empirically derived guidelines for effect size interpretation in social psychology. *European Journal of Social Psychology*, 51(3), 485–504. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ejsp.2752>
- Mayring, P. (2015). *Qualitative inhaltsanalyse: Grundlagen und techniken* (12th ed.). Dt. Studien-Verlag.
- Paivio, A. (1991). Dual coding theory: Retrospect and current status. *Canadian Journal of Psychology/Revue Canadienne de Psychologie*, 45(3), 255–287.
- Perlaviciute, G., Görsch, R., Timmerman, M., Steg, L., & Vrieling, L. (2021). Values in the backyard: The relationship between people's values and their evaluations of a real, nearby energy project. *Environmental Research Communications*, 3(10), Article 105004. <https://doi.org/10.1088/2515-7620/ac25d0>
- Perlaviciute, G., Schuitema, G., Devine-Wright, P., & Ram, B. (2018). At the heart of a sustainable energy transition: The public acceptability of energy projects. *IEEE Power and Energy Magazine*, 16(1), 49–55. <https://doi.org/10.1109/MPE.2017.2759918>
- R Core Team. (2023). *R: A Language and eEnvironment for Statistical Computing* [Computer software]. R Foundation for Statistical Computing <https://www.R-project.org/>.
- Regulation (EC). (2019). No 1059/2003 of the European parliament and of the council of 26 may 2003 on the establishment of a common classification of territorial units for statistics (NUTS). <http://data.europa.eu/eli/reg/2003/1059/2019-11-13/eng>.
- Siegrist, M., & Berthold, A. (2024). The lasting effect of the romantic view of nature: How it influences perceptions of risk and the support of symbolic actions against climate change. *Risk Analysis*. <https://doi.org/10.1111/risa.17672>. n/a(n/a).
- Starr, C. (1969). Social benefit versus technological risk. *Science*, 165(3899), 1232–1238. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.165.3899.1232>
- TNS Opinion & Social. (2010). *Special Eurobarometer 347: Electromagnetic Fields.: Report*. Tversky, A., & Kahneman, D. (1974). Judgment under uncertainty: Heuristics and biases. *Science*, 185(4157), 1124–1131.
- Unipark. (2023). *EFS Survey (Version Spring 2023)* [Computer software] <https://www.unipark.com/en/>.
- van der Horst, D. (2007a). NIMBY or not? Exploring the relevance of location and the politics of voiced opinions in renewable energy siting controversies. *Energy Policy*, 35(5), 2705–2714. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2006.12.012>
- van der Horst, D. (2007b). NIMBY or not? Exploring the relevance of location and the politics of voiced opinions in renewable energy siting controversies. *Energy Policy*, 35(5), 2705–2714. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2006.12.012>
- Vaupotić, N., Grellier, J., Martin, L., Panicello, C. D., Goszczyńska, E., Kojimahara, N., Polańska, K., Bauer, O., Mori, H., Yamaguchi-Sekino, S., Guxens, M., & White, M. P. (2025). 5G technology, health and society: Misconceptions, blind spots and insights from experts, non-experts, and self-identified electrosensitive individuals. *Journal of Risk Research*, 1–25. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13669877.2025.2512074>
- Verbeek, J., Oftedal, G., Feychting, M., van Rongen, E., Rosaria Scarfi, M., Mann, S., Wong, R., & van Deventer, E. (2021). Prioritizing health outcomes when assessing the effects of exposure to radiofrequency electromagnetic fields: A survey among experts. *Environment International*, 146, Article 106300. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envint.2020.106300>
- Verbeek, J., Zeeb, H., van Deventer, E., Ijaz, S., Doré, J.-F., Driessen, S., Roth, N., & Whaley, P. (2025). Systematic reviews and meta-analyses for the WHO assessment of health effects of exposure to radiofrequency electromagnetic fields, an introduction. *Environment International*. , Article 109751. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envint.2025.109751>
- VERBI Software. (2021). *MAXQDA (version 2022)* [Computer software].
- Wiedemann, P., Boerner, F., & Claus, F. (2018). How far is how far enough? Safety perception and acceptance of extra-high-voltage power lines in Germany. *Journal of Risk Research*, 21(4), 463–479. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13669877.2016.1220415>
- Wiedemann, P., & Claus, F. (2013). Mehr Akzeptanz durch striktere Grenzwerte? *EW Magazin Für Energiewirtschaft*, 2013, 50–53.
- World Health Organization. (2020). Radiation: 5G mobile networks and health. <https://www.who.int/news-room/questions-and-answers/item/radiation-5g-mobile-networks-and-health>.
- YouGov. (2021). *5G: Gauging concern around the world*. YouGov. <https://today.yougov.com/technology/articles/37105-5g-gauging-concern-around-world>.